

The Effect of Leadership, Recruitment, Training, Career Development on Employee Productivity of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of leadership style, recruitment, training, and career development toward employee work productivity of PT. Wasco Engineering Indonesia. The population of this study were 136 peoples employee PT. Wasco Engineering Indonesia. Sampling technique were slovin formula as much 101 peoples. This research was quantitative design with double linear regression analysis. The results of the study concluded that leadership style had a partially significant effect toward employee work productivity. recruitment had a partially significant effect toward employee work productivity, training had a partially significant effect toward employee work productivity, career development had a partially significant effect toward employee work productivity, and leadership style, recruitment, training, and career development together affect employee work productivity.

KEYWORDS: Employee Work Productivity, Leadership, Recruitment, Training, Career Development

INTRODUCTION

The development of the business world today is happening so fast, and competition is getting tougher and economic resources have forced business organisations and companies to be able to survive in difficult situations. Changes in the structure of the Indonesian market in free trade against the background of global issues also have a huge impact on the Indonesian business climate. One solution that can be done to face this competition is to increase competitiveness, both in terms of products and the quality of a company's production. The company is not enough just to have a large capital to achieve its goals but must be assisted by its employees. Therefore, between the company and employees must have cooperation to achieve the desired goals that are manifested in work productivity. Employee work productivity is a very important factor in supporting business success. High productivity will be very beneficial for both employers and employees, especially for their welfare.

A person's work productivity can be influenced by leadership factors, a good and appropriate recruitment process, continuous training, and equitable career development. Productivity is the ratio between the totality of expenses at a certain time divided by the totality of inputs during that period Mulyono (2013). Productivity is also a measure of the economic efficiency of organisational activities in using human resources to produce goods or services. PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia is part of Wah Seong Group Corporation Berhad, engaged in the International Oil and gas and Industrial Services group, namely the manufacture of offshore equipment, platforms, etc. such as offshore platforms, refinery plans, etc., and construction internationally. In terms of productivity achievement, PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia has not shown a significant increasing trend over the last 4 years, as shown in table 1, below.

Table 1. Production Target and Realisation Production of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia. Period: 2018-2021

Year	Production Target (Ton)	Production Realisation (Ton)	Realisation% Target Achievement
2018	1.260	980	77.77
2019	1.340	1.125	83.95
2020	1.350	1.080	80.00
2021	1.470	1.275	86.73

Source: Data Project Control Wasco Engineering Indonesia, 2021

Table 1 above informs that the achievement of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia's production target does not show high productivity. This is based on the achievement of production targets on average still below 100%. In addition, the production realisation shows an unstable trend, in the sense that there is no significant increase. The decline in production realisation from

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1,125 tonnes in 2019 to 1,080 tonnes in 2020 was influenced by the decline in economic growth, due to the impact of the coronavirus 19 pandemic that hit the whole world.

The productivity of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia, which does not show an increasing trend, is in line with the achievement of the work productivity targets of permanent employees, as in Table 2, below.

Table 2. Achievement of Employee Work Productivity Targets

Year	Achievement of Employee Productivity Targets (%)					Total (persons)
	>91% (persons)	80-90% (persons)	70%-79 (persons)	61%-69% (persons)	< 60% (persons)	
2018	12	14	32	30	9	97
2019	11	16	42	24	10	103
2020	14	21	36	16	8	95
2021	24	34	42	27	9	136

Source: Human Resources Departemen PT.Wasco Engineering Indonesia, 2022

Achievement of employee work productivity targets in table 2 is a categorization of the comparison between the target and the realisation of the achievement of work targets of permanent employees on average at PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia. The achievement of work productivity targets above 91% which are not met by all permanent employees is influenced by the knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes of employees who are not as expected. In measuring the success of work productivity, knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes of employees in carrying out their work are needed (Yusuf, 2015). Sukarna (2013) states that the factors that influence work productivity include the ability of company leaders. Leadership is the spearhead of the organisation that directs people and leverages other resources for the benefit of the organisation. In a general sense, leadership shows the process of a person's activities in leading, guiding, influencing or controlling the thoughts, feelings, or behaviour of others. In leading, a person has different leadership styles in achieving organisational goals. Mas'ud, (2014) states that leadership style is a leader's way or tactic in order to influence subordinates to achieve high performance, so that it correlates with organisational strategy. The leadership style implemented at PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia, based on researcher observations, is closer to the task-oriented leadership style. This can be seen from the measurement of employee work productivity which refers to the results of achieving employee work targets, and is applied consistently to all employees. However, there is still an authoritarian-oriented leadership style, which can be seen in making strategic policies in employee promotions, which causes problems in the field. Problems that arise, especially occur in the placement of a person at the managerial level who does not go through a hierarchy of positions from the bottom, so that it lacks field operational experience. This affects decision-making that does not listen to input and suggestions from subordinates who work in field operations. In increasing work productivity, Sunarsi (2018) states that a good recruitment process for prospective employees affects the company's work productivity. Recruitment is an effort to find and influence prospective workers to apply for job vacancies offered by a company (Hasibuan, 2019). Recruitment of prospective employees should meet the quality criteria and suitability for the type of work required. Based on the observations of researchers, the recruitment process of prospective employees at PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia is still not done properly, especially on the quality of employees to be recruited, and suitability for job jobs. This is due to a conflict of interest in the recruitment process carried out by internal individuals of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia. Employees who do not have quality and who do work not in accordance with their expertise will indirectly affect work productivity. For the development of employee knowledge and skills, continuous training activities are needed according to company needs. Haryati & Sibarani (2015) state that training has an effect in increasing employee productivity. Training is a systematic process to change employee behaviour in achieving organisational goals related to employee skills and abilities to carry out work. Training has a current orientation and helps employees to achieve certain skills and abilities to be successful in carrying out their work (Rivai, 2013). PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia in improving employee knowledge and skills has conducted various training activities through *on job training* and *external training*. However, in its implementation, the determination of training participants has not been carried out through strict selection, so that it cannot be utilised optimally by the company. In addition, since permanent employees are dominated by foreign nationals, in general, those who take part in external training are dominated by employees who have the status of foreign nationals. In improving the company's productivity, in addition to a strong leadership style, the right recruitment process, and continuous employee training, according to Sukarna (2013), factors that affect work productivity include sustainable and equitable career development. Career development is a process of improving one's work ability that encourages an increase in work performance in order to achieve the desired career (Ardana et.al, 2012).

Career development at PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia runs quite well, where promotions are made based on the achievement of work productivity and other criteria. However, it is still found in the determination of promotions that are not in accordance with

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the indicators of fair treatment, in the sense that promotions are carried out based on the interests of certain individuals, especially dominated by employees who are foreign nationals, which indicates nepotism. In addition, information about various promotional opportunities has not been carried out transparently.

The results of relevant research related to employee work productivity and influencing variables, as in table 3, below.

Table 3. Research Gap Relevant Research Employee Job Productivity (Y)

Independent Variable & Researcher	Influence of independent variables to dependent variables			
	X1 → Y	X2 → Y	X3 → Y	X4 → Y
1. Leadership (X1) Rina (2020), Baihaqi A & Suherman. H (2021), Latif (2015), Ratnasi & Riwu (2018), Mulia (2016),	(+)			
2. Recruitment (X2) Sunarsi (2018)		(+)		
3. Training (X3) Baihaqi A & Suherman. H (2021) Haryati & Sibarani (2015), sarwani <i>et.al</i> (2020), wayuningsih (2019), Sunarsi (2018)			(-) (+)	
4. Career Development (X4) Supendi & Harsum (2018)				(+)

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2022

Table 3 above reveals the research gap of relevant research results between the 4 independent variables and the dependent variable. The results showed that there was a positive influence of leadership style variables (X1), recruitment (X2), training (X3), and career development (X4) on employee work productivity (Y). However, there are differences in the results of Baihaqi's research. A & Suherman.H (2021) which states that training has a negative effect on work productivity, meaning that training has no effect on work productivity. In connection with the issues and facts, as well as the results of relevant research above, the research problem is formulated, namely, 1). Does leadership style affect the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia; 2). Does recruitment affect the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia; 3). Does training affect the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia; 4) Does career development affect the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia; and 5). Does leadership style, recruitment, training and career development simultaneously affect the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.

METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology

The type and research design used in this research is quantitative research. Quantitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism used to research on certain populations or samples, Siyoto and Sodik (2015). This study uses a descriptive design that aims to describe the variables studied and the dependence of the variables, thus producing comprehensive information about the variables studied.

Research Variables

Research variables are anything in the form of anything that is determined to be studied so that information about it is obtained, then Sugiyono (2016) draws conclusions. The variables in this study are leadership style (X1), recruitment (X2), training (X3), and career development (X4) as independent variables, and employee work productivity (Y) as the dependent variable.

Population and Samples

The research population is a generalisation area consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to study, and then draw conclusions, Sugiyono (2016). The population in this study were all permanent employees of both staff and field Wasco Engineering Indonesia as many as 136 people. The sampling procedure or sample size was carried out using the Slovin formula proposed by Siyoto, et.al (2015) as many as 101 people.

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Data Types and Sources

Primary data, namely data obtained directly from the original source of respondents through questionnaires. Secondary data, namely research data obtained indirectly through intermediary media that has been processed.

Data Collection Techniques

Data collection techniques are the means used by researchers in collecting their research data, Arikunto (2010). Data collection techniques using questionnaires and documentation. Questionnaires are written statements used to obtain information from respondents, in the sense of reports about personal or known things. Research data is also obtained from reports and other documents, which are closely related to the object of research and reading literature as a theoretical basis that will serve as a theoretical basis in this study.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis used an inferential statistical approach of multiple linear regression, with the help of SPSS 26.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' Characteristics

The characteristics of respondents are dominated by male gender at 86.13%. This condition is in accordance with the characteristics of the company's business activities in the field of petroleum construction. The age of employees is dominated by productive age, namely 31.68% at the age of 31-40 years, and 35.64% at the age of 41-50 years.

The education level of company employees is dominated by the Strata 1 level by 49.50% and the Diploma level by 34.65%. The length of service of company employees is dominated by 1-5 years by 42.57% and 6-10 years by 32.67%, this indicates that there is still a high level of human resource turnover at PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.

Descriptive Analyses

The results of descriptive testing of employee work productivity variables, leadership styles, recruitment, training, and career development on average show respondents' perceptions in the High category, as in table 4, below:

Table: 4 Respondents' Perceptions of Research Variables

Variabel	Value	Kategori
Employee Productivity	4,19	height
Leadership	3,55	Height
Recruitment	4,08	Height
Training	4,25	Height
Career Development	3,69	Height

Classical Assumption Test Normality Test

The normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution (Ghozali, 2016). A good regression model has normal or near normal data distribution. The results of the normality test in graphical analysis show the distribution of data on the normal P-P Plot graph, as in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Data Normality Graph

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2022

Based on Figure 1 above, the P-P Plot is around the transverse sloping line, so it can be concluded that the teacher performance

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data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether there is a correlation between the independent variables (free) and the dependent variable (bound) in a regression model. The multicollinearity test is carried out by looking at the variance inflation factor value. The test results using SPSS 26, obtained the results as in table 5, below:

Table 5 Multicollinearity Test Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	LEADERSHIP	,577	1,734
	RECRUITMENT	,696	1,437
	TRAININGS	,351	2,853
	CAREER DEVELOPMENT	,447	2,237

A: Dependent Variable: PRODUCTIVITY OF WORK

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2022

Based on table 5 above, it can be seen that all independent variables have a *tolerance* value greater than 10% (0.10), and the VIP value is smaller than 10, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in the regression model.

Heteroskedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether the regression model occurs in the same *variance* from residuals or other observations. If the variance of the residuals from one observation to another is constant, it is called homoscedasticity (Ghozali, 2016). Test heteroscedasticity in this regression by looking at the *residual scatter plot* pattern as in Figure 2, below:

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity test

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2022

From the output results in Figure 2 above, it can be seen that the dots do not form a clear pattern. The dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. So it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem in the regression model (Ghozali, 2016).

Hypothesis Testing Test “t”

The t test aims to determine the effect and significance of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The significance value ≤ 0.05 H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is an influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The t test, statistically, can be found by comparing the value of tcount with ttable, with the provisions;

- If $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$, H_0 is rejected and H_1 accepted
- If $t_{hitung} < t_{tabel}$, H_0 accepted, and H_1 is rejected

Multiple linear regression equations and t values, as in table 6, follow.

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Table 6 Multiple Linear Regression and t-test Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,999	1,883		7,040	,003
LEADERSHIP	,241	,072	,195	3,336	,001
RECRUITMENT	,418	,084	,264	4,964	,000
TRAININGS	,510	,078	,489	6,514	,000
CAREER DEVELOPMENT	,086	,039	,146	2,197	,030

a. Dependent Variable: PRODUCTIVITY OF WORK

Source: Processed Primary Data 2022

Based on table 7, the regression equation for the variables of leadership style, recruitment, training and career development on work productivity is:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + e$$

$Y = 2,999 + 0,241X_1 + 0,418X_2 + 0,510X_3 + 0,086X_4 + e$ and the results of the t test, partially the variables of leadership style, recruitment, training, and career development have a significant effect on work productivity.

Test- F

The F test is used to determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable. The results of the F test, as in table 7, are as follows.

Table 7 Test- F ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	4063,996	4	1015,999	102,686	,000 ^b
Residual	949,846	96	9,894		
Total	5013,842	100			

a. Dependent Variable: PRODUCTIVITY OF WORK

b. Predictors: (Constant), LEADERSHIP, RECRUITMENT, TRAINING, CAREER DEVELOPMENT

Source: Processed Primary Data

Based on table 8 above, the significance results F_{hitung} the Value is $102,686 > F_{table} 2,46$ and the significance of F is $0,000 (< 0,05)$, which means that the four leadership style variables (X_1), recruitment (X_2), Training (X_3), dan career development (X_4) together have a very significant effect on the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

Coefficient of determination (R^2) in essence, it is used to measure how far the model's ability to explain the dependent variable. Coefficient of determination (R^2) has a range 0 until 1 ($0 < R^2 < 1$). The greater the value of R^2 (almost 1) then it means that the effect of independent variables simultaneously is considered strong and if R^2 (almost 0) then it means that the effect of independent variables simultaneously is considered weak. The results of the coefficient of determination test, as in table 8, are as follows.

Table 8 Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2) Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,900 ^a	,811	,803	3,14551	1,848

a. Predictors: (Constant), LEADERSHIP, RECRUITMENT, TRAINING, CAREER DEVELOPMENT,

b. Dependent Variable: PRODUKTIVITAS KERJA

Source: Processed Primary Data. 2022

Based on table 9, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R Square) obtained is 0.803 or 80.30%. This means that the dependent variable of employee work productivity can be explained by leadership style (X_1), recruitment (X_2),

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training (X3), and career development (X4) by 80.30%, while the remaining 19.70% is explained by other factors, apart from the variables of leadership style, recruitment, training and career development.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate; 1). There is a significant effect of leadership style (X1) on employee work productivity (Y), and in line with the results of research by Rina (2020) and Baihaqi (2021) which state that leadership style has a significant effect on employee work productivity; 2). There is a significant effect of recruitment (X2) on employee work productivity (Y), and in line with the results of Sunarsi's research (2018) which found recruitment has a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity; 3). There is a significant effect of training (X3) on employee work productivity (Y), and in line with the results of research by Haryati & Sibarani (2015), and Sarwani et.al (2020) who found training has a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity. However, the results of Baihaqi and Suherman's research (2021) state that training has no significant effect on employee work productivity; 4). There is a significant effect of career development (X4) on employee work productivity (Y), and in line with the results of research by Supendi & Harsum (2018) which states that career development factors statistically have a positive effect on efforts to increase employee work productivity at the PT Post Office (Persero) Kendari; and 5). Leadership style variables, recruitment, training and career development variables simultaneously have a significant effect on employee work productivity, this is influenced by employee training that is scheduled and carried out on an ongoing basis, and can indirectly improve career development, thus ultimately affecting the increase in employee productivity of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.

CONCLUSIONS AND ADVICE

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it is concluded, as follows:

1. Leadership style has a significant effect on the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.
2. Recruitment has a significant effect on the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.
3. Training has a significant effect on the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.
4. Training has a significant effect on the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.
5. Leadership style, recruitment, training and career development together have a significant effect on the work productivity of employees of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.

Advice

As middle and top management positions are dominated by foreign nationals, the leadership style should be adapted to conditions and situations that are more suitable to the environment and atmosphere of the people in Indonesia. In recruiting new employee candidates, PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia needs to increase fair transparency, because transparent recruitment will be able to obtain qualified and professional prospective employees. To improve the quality of training, it is necessary to pay attention to good selection in determining trainees who meet the criteria and according to the specifications and needs of the field of work, this will be able to influence to improve employee career development. To obtain and strengthen the results of research on the influence of leadership style, recruitment, training and career development on employee work productivity, it is necessary to conduct research with a broader scope in a similar unit of analysis with the industry of PT Wasco Engineering Indonesia.

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